

A Study on QWL among the Employees of Public and Private Sector Banks in Tiruchirappalli District

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Abstract

The term quality of work life (QWL) was originally introduced in the late 1960's as a way of focusing on the effects of employment on worker health and general well being, and a way to enhance the quality of a person's on-the-job knowledge. Conversely there are generally recognized issue related to QWL like pay and stability of employment, occupational stress, alternative work schedule, recognition, participative management, gripe method, these measures will affect organizational concert in terms of human resource management. Organizations are estimated to maintain high Quality of Work Life in sort sustain top organizational performance. This study is an attempt to examine the level to which the QWL among the employees of public and private banks at Tiruchirappalli influences the performances of banks.

Keywords: Quality of work life, organizational performance, public and private banks, QWL

Introduction

Human capital is proposed as one of the input resources on which companies build their competitive advantage (Becker and Gerhart, 1996; Boxall, 1996; Tyson, 1995). While the beginning of the 1980's, a vast literature has been developed calling for a more strategic role for human resource (guest, 1987). The increasing interest in human resource due to the assumption that employees with the way they are managed is critical to the success of business and can be a basis of sustainable competitive advantage. In many ways, quality of work life represents a amalgamation of the very real concern for human values in today's society by means of an alertness the tall individual devote the greater part of their mature life to work, expanding time, energy, physical and mental resources to this endeavor (Subbarao, Neelima Alfred, 2003).

Employee satisfaction at the quality of work life directly affects the company's ability to suitably save its customers, and if it's not measured, it cannot be effective. QWL the measurement will help to inflict and organizational change, which is most appropriate for the service organization such as a bank. The need to commence and change will place increasing stress on management leadership skills (Rajesh Bagga, Garima Arora, Sanjev Arora, 2008).

Quality of Work Life

Quality of work life is a attitude, a set of values which hold the people are mainly important resource in the organization as they are dependable, accountable and capable of making an important contribution and they should be treat with dignity and respect (Straw and Heckscher 1984). QWL encompasses form of wages payment, working conditions, working time, health hazards issue, financial as well as non financial benefits and management behavior towards employees (Islam and Siengthai 2009). According to Gadon (1984), QWL programs have to objectives: (a) to enhance productivity and (b) to increase the satisfaction of employees. Thus QWL provide healthier, satisfied and productive employees, which in turn provide efficient and profitable organization (Sadique 2003).

Quality of Work Life in Banks

The fast movement of the banking industry toward improved mechanization in the 1970's may be an example of this contest to see which institutions could handle behavior quickest. Later, banks twisted to quality of work life programs, and employee participation teams finally come in to their own in the 1980's. During a changing an intensely a spirited era, remembering this ancient contest can be instructive as we look for new ways to solve previous problems in the 1990's.

Due to bank's broad spectrum of exposure across industries, their performance is deliberate as a substitute for an economy as a whole. Unfortunately in India, the banking sector as historically remained under the impact of non competitiveness poor technology integration, high NPAs and grossly under productive manpower. Banking sector in India as a broad mix, compressing of joint sector, nationalized sector, specialized corporate financial institution, supportive sector and foreign sector (Rajesh bagga, Garema arrora, Sanjev arrora 2008).

Banks want both bottom line and longer tenure improvements that more clearly link productivity to enhance competitive posture through better service quality. Experienced observation, dating back to the early experiments at the Hawthorne Western Electric plant, have shown that most excellence and some excellence of output gains are connected intimately with change in the traits of work life for employees, as determined by how people feel about their role in the organization (Herff L.Moore, William T. Bounds, 1993).

Quality of Work Life and Employee Performance

Quality of work life and employee presentation frequently go hand in hand, for one thing, most circumstances that add to performance like equitable salaries, financial incentives and efficient employee choice we also put in the QWL. In fact, every individual related action affect the QWL in some way (Subba RO, Neeleme Alfered, 2003). This will be achieve through such approach as: individual development programs, increased team effort and teamwork across all levels of the organizations including labor/ management partnership councils, and the commitment through doing a good and quality performance skilled based pay and shared possession of responsibilities might be two kinds of approach that will assist in improving performance on the work

Among the main center included in this text is the payment aspects. Remuneration aspects such as salary, salary increment, bonuses, allowances, pension as well as medical benefits are among the best examples that can motivate worker to give their best for the employer.

A research entitled "Quality of work life: implication Of Carrier Dimensions" (2006) by Radua Che Rose, LooSee Beh, Jegak Uli and Khairuddin Idris, supports the proposal of the degree of satisfaction in QWL is related to the degree to which individual believe his or her success criteria have been met. A study by Okpara (2004); Oshagbemi (2000) and Sloane and Williams (1996) who tinted difference in remuneration aspects conventional by the employee will abruptly affect

their work fulfillment and work recital Porter and Lawler (1968) identified three types of concert. First is regarding to productivity, second, concerning ratings of individuals by somebody other than the persons whose performance is being measured. Self –appraisal as well as self-ratings become the third type of performance. (Mohan and Ashok, 2011) Thus, job performance measures the level of achievements of business and social objectives and errands from the perception of the judging party (Hersey and Blanchard, 1993). The labors of civilizing QWL and humanizing the labor force do not show a consistent relationship to productivity. QWL programs result in highly energetic and committed employees. Most approach to improve the quality of work life have ramification throughout the organization and possibly outside the organization as well. Excellent participative management, cooperation as well as time management are mainly apparent outcomes. Evidence indicates that if QWL programs are conduct properly, they can yield a substantial return on investment by increasing productivity, decreasing cost and prevent accidents and expenditure. As indicated earlier, positive aspects of QWL consequences in organization’s excellence in human resource behavior (Suba Rao, Neelema Alfred, 2003).

Research Objectives

- To study the relationship between quality of work life and satisfaction level of employees in banks of Trichirappalli.
- To study the relationship between QWL and organizational performance.

Research Methodology

The study mainly based on primary data. From the review of literature the original research started by clarifying and defining the nature of problems related to quality of work life. Further the descriptive research this designed to describe characteristics of organizations with regard to QWL.

Although the population for the study consist of all the employees of public and private sector bank in Tiruchirappalli only yet the result could be generalized to the banking sector as a whole. The sample chosen is based on convenience sampling method. Respondents were selected based on their compliance to provide pertinent information. The responses of the respondents to the structure questionnaire be composed in a licked scale are numbered from 1 to 5. The data collected through questionnaire from their employees of various banks are being analyzed and the results of data analysis are shown through follow tables.

Table 1 Relationship between perception of QWL among the employees of Private Banks (QWL1) and Public Banks (QWL2) in Tiruchirappalli

QWL Components	Correlation coefficient 'r' with QWL1	Correlation coefficient 'r' with QWL2	R1	R2	Difference of Rank D (R1- R2)	D2
Acknowledgement	0.62	0.73	19	17	2	4
Challenge	0.73	0.83	14	8	6	36
Dialogue	0.23	0.21	21	21	0	0
Direction	0.75	0.80	11	10	1	1
Equality	0.85	0.90	6	4	2	4
Fit	0.25	0.27	20	20	0	0
Flexibility	0.75	0.85	11	6	5	25
Informality	0.70	0.74	17	15	2	4

Invention	0.73	0.86	14	5	9	81
Oneness	0.71	0.75	16	13	3	9
Ownership	0.78	0.73	9	17	-8	64
Personal development	0.95	0.92	1	2	-1	1
Purpose	0.85	0.80	6	10	-4	16
Relationship building	0.90	0.95	3	7	-4	16
Relevance	0.85	0.80	6	10	-4	16
Respect	0.90	0.95	3	1	2	4
Self identify	0.90	0.91	3	3	0	0
Service	0.75	0.70	11	19	-8	64
Support	0.69	0.75	18	13	5	25
Validation	0.73	0.73	14	17	-3	9
Worth	0.80	0.75	8	13	-5	25

Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient

$$P = 1 - \frac{6 \sum D^2}{N(N^2 - 1)}$$

$$\sum D^2 = 404, \text{ and } N = 21,$$

By substituting the values in the above equation, the value of p = 0.7377

$$df = N-2 \text{ that is } 19$$

The critical ratio of p at 0.5 levels, df 19 is 0.388

The calculated value of p (0.7377) > critical ratio of p (0.388), Hence there is some significant relationship between the apparent QWL of the employees of private sector banks and apparent QWL of the employees of public sector banks.

Table 2 Correlation between the perceived QWL and perceived performance among the employees of public sector banks in Tiruchirappalli

		Perceived QWL among Public Sector Bank employees	Perceived performance in Public Sector Banks
Perceived QWL among Public Sector Bank Employees	Pearson correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 15	0.938 15
Perceived performance in Public Sector Banks	pearson correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.938 .000 15	1 15

Correlation is Significant at the 0.01 level (2- tailed).

The correlation coefficient “r” value is 0.938, perfect positive correlation, hence there is a significant relationship between the perceived QWL and apparent performance among the employees of public sector banks in Tiruchirappalli.

Table 3 Correlation between the perceived QWL and perceived performance among the employees of private sector banks in Tiruchirappalli

		Perceived QWL among Private Sector Bank employees	Perceived performance in Private sector banks
Perceived QWL among Private Sector Bank Employees	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 15	.909 .000 15
Perceived performance in Private Sector Banks	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.909 .000 15	1 15

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation coefficient “r” value is 0.909, perfect positive correlation, hence there is a significant relationship between the perceived QWL and perceived performance among the employees of private sector banks in Tiruchirappalli.

Discussion

The objective of study was to examine the survival, feature and degree of the linear relationship exist between QWL and the components of QWL from the literature review 21 components QWL were recognized. The components were connected with the perceived QWL both public and private sector banks. The association of correlation coefficient of both categories shows the existence of significant relationship between QWL among the employees of both sectors. Table -1 shows the relationship between perception of QWL among the employees of private bank (QWL1) and public banks (QWL2) in Tiruchirappalli. Table 2 and Table 3 shows the correlation among the perceived QWL and pursued performance amongst the employees of public sector banks and correlation between the perceived QWL and perceived performance among the employees of private sector banks in Tiruchirappalli, it shows ideal optimistic relationship between QWL and performance in both the sectors.

Conclusion

Human behavior is unpredictable and multifaceted in life, and it is needed to be study in some organization for effective utilization and functioning of human resources. Organizational quality has high impact on the levels of QWL in an organization. The Antecedents of QWL like job stability, climate, presentation and growth, endorsement, welfare measures with a range of other factors directly affect the organizational excellence. The performance of organization can be improved only when the human resources of contented with the higher quality of working life. The methods of enhancing QWL by improve the existing job environment.

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